

Current needs and challenges on data retention, appraisal, and reappraisal across stakeholders and communities

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¹ This paper is a collaborative effort by the LTDR TF members. Authors worked in groups to address different challenges, and they are listed in alphabetical order. While not all authors contributed to every challenge description, all were invited to review the full document. Some challenges prompted extensive discussions, and the viewpoints reflected in this version may evolve in future updates. The editors, who are the Task Force co-chairs, consolidated and refined the nine challenges into a coherent deliverable report for publication. Reviewers include the LTDR TF Board Liaison and invited external experts.

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Executive summary

This paper is one of the deliverable reports from the EOSC Association's Long-Term Data Retention Task Force, focusing on the current needs and challenges related to long-term data retention. It provides an overview of the main issues faced by a wide range of stakeholders and communities regarding data retention, appraisal, and reappraisal, along with proposed solutions or recommendations addressing each identified challenge.

In total, nine key challenges are described in this report, based on the discussions and efforts of the Task Force. Several potential solutions or recommendations are provided for each identified challenge, encouraging relevant stakeholders and communities to consider them in their future practices. We also observed cross-links between challenges, as some challenges may contribute to issues described in others, and certain solutions may apply to multiple challenge areas. While we acknowledge that additional challenges may exist beyond the scope of this document, we hope that this report will serve as a valuable resource for data curators, data managers, and other interested stakeholders. Several topics remain crucial to long-term data retention, and we aim to continue improving this document in an updated version, so that we can further support ongoing efforts to strengthen the sustainability and preservation of research data within EOSC and beyond.

The target audience includes professionals working in data curation, retention, and long-term preservation, across research, education, government, and industry sectors.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full term
LTDR-TF	Long-Term Data Retention Task Force
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
TDRs	Trustworthy Digital Repositories
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Europe and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
ATMPs	Advanced therapy medicinal products
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
DMP	Data management plan
RPO	Research performing organisations
maDMPs	Machine-actionable DMPs

Introduction

During 2024-2025, the Long-Term Data Retention (LTDR) Task Force was organized and reviewed the landscape of long-term data retention across the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Association. In preparing this deliverable, the LTDR Task Force gathered information from members and stakeholders to map existing practices, identify challenges, and document the governance structures and policy considerations that influence long-term data retention across disciplines and communities.

The LTDR Task Force builds upon and complements the work of the Long-Term Data Preservation Task Force, which focused primarily on the technical, infrastructural, and policy aspects of ensuring trustworthy long-term preservation of research data. The LTDR Task Force explores what data should be retained, the minimum requirements for retention, the duration of retention, and the conditions under which data should be preserved. Together, both initiatives provide a more holistic understanding of sustainable data stewardship in the EOSC context.

The work of the LTDR Task Force is also closely linked with related Horizon Europe projects such as EOSC EDEN² and FIDELIS³, which focus on developing and implementing comprehensive digital preservation strategies and establishing a Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs) network within the EOSC ecosystem. The LTDR Task Force has leveraged insights from these projects to examine the challenges associated with data identification, retention strategies, and governance frameworks.

Research data are often stored across a diverse and fragmented landscape of repositories and storage solutions, including institutional repositories, national archives, domain-specific repositories, and commercial cloud services. These repositories can differ significantly in their funding models, governance structures, and technological infrastructure, which may lead to inconsistencies in accessibility, metadata standards, data quality, and long-term sustainability. In this report, members of the LTDR Task Force have collaboratively identified nine key challenges. These, along with proposed solutions, are presented below:

- Challenge 1: Funding constraints
- Challenge 2: Lack of expertise
- Challenge 3: Discipline and content specific challenges
- Challenge 4: Lack of standards, guidelines and policies

² EOSC EDEN. <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/eosc-eden/>

³ FIDELIS. <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/fidelis/>

- Challenge 5: Understanding the value of data holdings
- Challenge 6: Technological challenges
- Challenge 7: Legal challenges
- Challenge 8: Ethical challenges
- Challenge 9: Trust

A Vision for Long-Term Data Retention and Its Challenges

Data retention is fundamental to ensuring research integrity, reproducibility, and accountability of scientific discoveries and outcomes, allowing researchers to verify and build upon previous findings. It also facilitates the use of advanced analytical methodologies, such as metadata analysis and large-scale language modelling. It underpins knowledge preservation and responsible data governance for future research and policy making. In the digital era, our datasets and digital records also form a vital part of our historical record and cultural heritage. Disciplines that build cumulatively on prior research particularly benefit from long-term access to datasets, particularly in developing and supporting longitudinal studies. Moreover, making data available for cross-disciplinary reuse fosters innovative approaches and new insights. Data retention needs to balance the need for long-term preservation with considerations such as security, privacy, cost, and the data's value and relevance to a specific context, subject matter or community..

Data retention also serves to meet legal, ethical, and institutional obligations. It ensures compliance with data protection frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation ([GDRP, Regulation 2016/679](#)) in Europe and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) ([CDC, 2024](#)) in the United States, which define how personal and medical data should be stored, processed, and deleted. Specific regulatory frameworks, such as EU legislation on clinical trials, mandate minimum retention periods: for example, the clinical trial master file must be archived for 25 years, and for trials involving advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs), a minimum retention period of 30 years is required. Clearer data retention and sharing policies benefit not only the research community but also industry, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), journalists, and the public. Open and transparent access to data fosters trust in institutions, supports evidence-based decision making, and enhances collaboration between public and private sectors.

Stakeholders and Responsibilities

In this document, stakeholders are the individuals or groups with an interest in or influence over data retention practices — such as researchers, institutions, funders, policymakers, and

data service providers – each with differing priorities regarding access, privacy, cost, and technology use (See Figure 1). Stakeholders have varying expectations, ranging from open accessibility to strict data privacy, as well as cost-efficiency and technology adoption. One challenge for a broad data retention strategy is to account for such differing interests while addressing the longevity, usability, and legal compliance of the data, in order to develop strategies that are sustainable and practical. In this context, the groups of stakeholders we identify are:

- **Data creators and owners** refer to individuals or organizations that generate or collect the data, and data owners are responsible for the data or dataset’s integrity, quality, and usage. Data creators and owners can be the same or different (when rights or licenses are assigned to someone other than the creator), even for the same data. Data creators and owners encompass a broad spectrum of individuals, organizations, and institutions. These include researchers and academic institutions that are responsible for generating, managing, and preserving research data to support future studies and foster cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- **Data stewards and repositories** – focusing on data curation, metadata management, and maintaining long-term data quality and integrity.
- **Open-source tools digital preservation communities** – developing and maintaining interoperable, sustainable tools and platforms for digital preservation.
- **Commercial preservation tools and service providers** – offering professional preservation services and solutions (e.g., Preservica, Arkivum, Artefactual, Libnova, Ex Libris, ITHAKA).
- **Legal and ethical oversight bodies** – ensuring data compliance, integrity, and sovereignty through appropriate governance and regulatory frameworks.
- **Policy makers and funders** – long-term data retention supports the evaluation of past interventions and the design of more effective responses to contemporary challenges such as climate change, public health crises, and socioeconomic inequalities ([Tsipouri et al., 2025](#)). They can support compliance with legal standards and Open Science mandates, particularly those requiring open access to data produced with public funding. They also play a key role in establishing cost-effective, transparent, and sustainable preservation policies.
- **The general public** – including journalists and independent researchers, whose access to scientific data enhances transparency, accountability, and public trust.

Figure 1. Overview of stakeholders involved in data retention practices.

Retention periods and reappraisal triggers

Retention periods and reappraisal triggers should be clearly defined to ensure that data are retained (and potentially preserved) as needed, while also taking into account the costs of infrastructure and storage. Certain datasets—such as genomic records or climate models—may require retention for indefinite periods, whereas others may become obsolete due to technological advances or shifts in disciplinary relevance. Establishing structured re-

appraisal triggers and regular review cycles supports informed decision-making regarding the retention, curation, preservation, or deletion of datasets.

When planning data retention timelines, a range of factors and questions should be considered. For instance, if an institution ceases to exist or changes its mission, what becomes of its digital repository? Where can the data be transferred, and under what conditions? Are there national or European archives able to assume responsibility? Is there a need for an “Repository of last resort” specifically dedicated to institutional, disciplinary, or certified repositories? What happens to the data after the retention period ends? How can its archiving potential be assessed? These questions highlight the many uncertainties surrounding the end of retention, which may arise from various institutional, technical, or legal factors.

Data Characteristics

Research data vary widely in type, format, and processing state, which directly affects how data are stored, accessed, and preserved. In the context of data retention, researchers, data stewards or organizations often manage multiple types of data generated throughout the research or operational lifecycle. Another delivery report from LTDR Task Force, on the conceptual framework for the implementation of the Retention, (Re)Appraisal - Iterative Logic (RRAIL)⁴, describes more detailed characteristics of digital objects submitted to the repository, also see Figure 2.

⁴ The delivery report, “Conceptual framework on the implementation of workflows concerning Retention (Re) Appraisal - Iteration Logic (RRAIL)” will be published concurrently with this document.

Figure 2. Example characteristics for a digital object submitted into a repository, derived from another deliverable report of the TDRF TF.

Examples of data types include, but are not limited to:

- **Scientific research output** – experimental and computational outputs such as measurements, models, analytical code, simulations, and derived datasets; as well as observational data collected through sensors, surveys, satellites, or fieldwork.
- **Historical and cultural data** – longitudinal datasets, interviews, archival records, digitised texts, cultural heritage collections, visual and performing arts, as well as museum or library holdings that preserve historical and societal information.
- **Commercial and industry data** – data generated in private-sector contexts, including market and business intelligence, operational datasets, and information produced through collaborations or public–private partnerships. These are often subject to licensing, intellectual property restrictions, and defined usage limitations.

Given the diverse nature of data, adopting standardized metadata schemas and persistent identifiers helps achieve findability and interoperability across repositories, and it also supports reuse and interdisciplinary work. Metadata completeness, transparency in licensing, and format sustainability are furthermore important for maintaining long-term usability. Data can also be distinguished by processing stage:

- **Raw data** – collected directly from a source and saved without additional processing, with mechanisms in place to ensure originality.
- **Processed data** – raw data that have been cleaned, structured, or otherwise prepared to be suitable for analysis or research purposes.
- **Derived data** – data generated by applying analytical methods, algorithms, or transformations to raw or processed data, resulting in new values or models.

Key data characteristics include provenance, temporal/spatial coverage, sensitivity, licensing/access/permissions. Metadata and persistent identifiers are essential for supporting interoperability, discoverability, and long-term usability. Standardized metadata schemas improve dataset reusability and cross-disciplinary collaboration, while persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) provide stable links for citation and version control. Various metadata standards exist, ranging from broadly applicable schemas—such as Dublin Core or DataCite—to domain-specific standards, like ISO 19115 for geographic data. Domain-focused standards facilitate specialized searches and support discipline-specific reuse.

Data Retention Challenges and Proposed Solutions

Challenge 1: Funding Constraints⁵

4.1.1 Description of the challenge

Ensuring the long-term preservation of data and its associated metadata remains a complex challenge that requires ongoing dialogue among data creators, archival service providers including research performing organisations, and funding bodies. A persistent set of challenges stems from funding constraints affecting the viability and sustainability of long-term data preservation efforts. These challenges can be grouped into five key areas:

- **Funding gap:** Research funding is typically structured to support activities within the defined lifespan of a project. For instance, under the Horizon Europe framework⁶ projects generally span two to five years. While some retention and preservation costs can be anticipated and front-loaded during the project, the need to maintain

⁵ A revised version of this section (Funding Constraints) will be worked on by the Long Term Data Retention Task Force in 2026.

⁶https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

data beyond the funding period remains. This includes ensuring that data can be discovered, understood, and accessed for a long time, a requirement that is often not funded once the project ends.

- **Unclear Responsibility:** There is frequently a lack of clarity regarding who holds the responsibility for data after a project ends (Wallis & Borgman, 2011) . Potential custodians include the original researchers, their host institutions, funding agencies, or dedicated archival services, both public and private. This ambiguity leads to inconsistent practices and a general reluctance to engage with long-term archiving, particularly when roles and expectations are not formally defined.
- **Unequal Distribution of Costs and Benefits:** While preserved data generates long-term value for a broad community - including future researchers, educators, and policymakers - the costs of preservation are borne by a narrow set of actors. This imbalance often leads to a disproportionate sharing of financial responsibility and insufficient or uneven investment in sustainable data infrastructure.
- **Fragmented Archive Landscape:** The archival ecosystem is fragmented, with archives often siloed by data type, sector, discipline, or domain. Each archive may operate under different policies, standards, and levels of support, making interoperability and data migration difficult. This fragmentation becomes particularly problematic when archives lose funding or are decommissioned, as it complicates efforts to transfer or replicate data across systems.
- **Underfunded Archives:** Many archives operate without dedicated or stable funding streams. Funding bodies tend to prioritise innovation and new research over the maintenance of existing infrastructure. Consequently, essential activities such as ensuring data remains accessible, usable, and secure, are overlooked or underfunded. This lack of financial support undermines the long-term viability of archives and the data they hold.

4.1.2 Recommendations

To address the various challenges posed by funding constraints, here are some recommended practices.

- **Introduce dedicated post-project preservation funding mechanisms.** These could be structured as separate grants or extensions specifically earmarked for data stewardship beyond the project lifecycle. Funders like Horizon Europe could consider adding a mandatory preservation phase to project budgets, ensuring that data remains accessible and usable after the research concludes. Permanent preservation represents a challenging funding model. One potential approach is to draw inspiration

from private-sector solutions, where companies offer platforms for permanent cloud storage of personal media and documents for a single upfront payment.

- **Establish clear data preservation policies and agreements at the outset of research projects.** These should define who is responsible for long-term preservation, ideally aligned to institutional policies or funder mandates. Assigning responsibility to institutions or designated public repositories can help standardise practices.
- **Recognize the importance of data preservation.** Encourage data preservation by recognising its importance in impact assessments and future funding decisions. This could include investing in education on FAIR principles and promoting data reuse, as well as creating dedicated growth areas focused on FAIR practices.
- **Encourage interoperability and standardisation across archives through promoting the adoption of common metadata standards, APIs, and data formats.** Funders and international bodies could support initiatives that foster collaboration between archives and promote the development of federated or networked archival systems.
- **Create sustainable funding streams for archives, including core infrastructure support.** This could involve long-term institutional commitments, national funding programmes, or international collaborations. Funders should recognise the importance of ongoing “maintenance” activities and allocate resources accordingly, ensuring that archives can continue to provide access and support without relying solely on project-based funding.

Challenge 2: Lack of expertise

4.2.1 Description of the challenge

Throughout its lifecycle—being produced, stored, used, and eventually archived or deleted—data passes through multiple stages, each requiring specific skills and knowledge. Individual researchers, institutions, and organizations are increasingly confronted with advanced technologies, growing administrative demands, and complex legislation. In these evolving situations, experts in every field are becoming increasingly essential.

- **Limited awareness among researchers about the importance of data retention.** From a researcher’s perspective, resources (e.g., time, money, focus) are often allocated on the acquisition and processing of data so as to yield publishable results. Data retention is often merely seen as a secondary concern and is therefore usually only practiced to fulfill a funder/policy requirement. When the publication cycle is treated not as a goal but merely as a compliance requirement, the incentive to develop skills related to data retention is often overlooked—or entirely missing. This

situation can differ, however, in many longitudinal studies that retain data for the long-term needs of their own research (e.g., ecological monitoring, longitudinal health studies, or studies of long-lived animal species). Such projects typically have stronger motivation to invest in data retention and often employ dedicated data stewards or database managers to support this work.

- **Missing workflows, documentation, and skills in data transfer workflows, data documentation, and staff with dedicated expertise.**
 - **Workflow.** Another challenge in the field of data retention is the absence of workflows. Different stakeholders (e.g., researchers, computing center data engineers, archivists) take care of data at various stages of the lifecycle. There are also different storage/preservation infrastructures, and data often gets transferred from one to another throughout the retention process (e.g., data may be transferred from an institutional service meant for active use to a national service meant for passive retention). The transfer of data between infrastructures requires workflows to ensure integrity, and it also requires workflows and trained/informed staff to ensure the chain of transfer of custody is not broken as the data is handed to and from distinct shareholders.
 - **Skills.** Besides retaining data, skills are also needed to complete proper documentation (both human and machine-readable) that accompanies the data. In other words, data should be retained in a way that ensures it is reusable. Achieving this requires a broad set of competencies, ranging from technical to non-technical skills. These include knowledge of databases and best practices for structuring and describing data; proficiency with classification tools and automated metadata generation; analytical skills; familiarity with various documentation tools; and strong communication and organizational abilities. The overarching goal is to ensure that data can be easily understood for its original purpose and reused for future research in a straightforward and efficient manner. This is only possible if the stored data is accompanied by clear, understandable, and well-structured documentation. Another increasingly important and in-demand skill is the ability to understand current regulations and legal frameworks, and to apply them correctly. This includes identifying sensitive data that must be properly handled and documented, so they can be readily recognized and accessed only by authorized users and organizations. Data repository management roles within institutions are also often altogether missing or being carried out by data stewards or research support staff not necessarily trained to do so.

Misplacing the care of an institutional repository at the operational rather than at the managerial or strategic level makes the creation of policies required to manage a repository a challenging if not impossible task.

- **Training.** Training in data retention is not always available, and trainers often lack the necessary technical skills. In terms of training researchers in data retention, this is often done by the university data management support team. Such a team can be run/coordinated by the university library, sometimes in collaboration with the IT department. However, hiring dedicated data engineers or data managers for these teams is often not feasible due to salary, budget, or governance constraints. As a result, research support staff tend to rely more on soft skills and general knowledge of the data management life cycle rather than the technical expertise needed for effective data retention (e.g., data and databases engineers, storage and cloud system engineers, software engineers for the implementation of automations). In many cases, resources are insufficient to build data support teams where dedicated personnel can focus solely on data retention. In addition, awareness of the importance of data retention has emerged recently, leaving support teams with limited time to develop the necessary specialization and technical capabilities.
- **Lack of continuity in temporary, project-based data steward positions.** Hiring data stewards solely on a project-to-project basis cramps the need for them to obtain and/or apply any data retention skills. This is because their role as custodians of the data ends shortly when data retention begins. Also, data stewards may not have the incentive to train other project members in data retention skills due to this lack of continuity.
- **Missing policies and best practices on data custody.** Another challenge arises in the case of a retiring or departing researcher; the lack of a service or dedicated person who can check and ensure that the relevant data has been deposited in a trustworthy (domain specific) repository according to institutional policies. In other words, someone needs to be responsible for ensuring that all necessary steps are taken—whether this falls to data support teams, the HR department, or another designated unit. It should not be solely the responsibility of the retiring researcher to deposit their data. When “testamentated” data is left to a university, additional challenges arise regarding data rights. Other researchers may hold rights to the same data, and identifying or contacting them can require significant effort, especially if the research team is large or dispersed.

- Inadequate security management practices.** Another challenge lies in the differing interpretations of sensitive data and the protection levels required for various types of research data. In some cases, security levels are determined based on official document classifications—but do these directly correspond to research data protection? For example, does a confidential document equate to sensitive research data? In other words, retaining sensitive research data brings its own challenges and requires extra skills, both technically and practically (e.g., managing access rights and ensuring the chosen service meets the appropriate security level). Compounding this, there is a generally limited availability of dedicated services or repositories for sensitive data retention.

Insufficient expertise in data retention exists at all levels, including repository management, data providers, data management, researchers (including retired or temporary contract workers), and knowledge loss, see Table 1 below.

Table 1. An overview of the insufficient expertise regarding data retention.

Expertise Level	Description
Repository management level	Archivists or digital data experts must have a combination of skills that ensure the creation of valuable, trustworthy, and secure information by following well known standards, best practices, and conventions. Compliance with these evolving criteria requires updates that depend on continuous technological developments, past-present-future needs, and consistency with shifting laws and regulations (internal, national, EU, international level).
Storage systems level	Specialists responsible for maintaining storage systems play a vital role in ensuring that storage infrastructures remain fully operational, secure, and resilient throughout their entire lifecycle.
Depositor level	An expert at the depositor level must ensure that data is correctly submitted and sufficiently and appropriately described to support its easy discovery and proper reuse. At the same time, they must ensure that the policies in force are followed and properly applied.
Data management	Processed data should always refer to specific projects and be consistent

level	and closely bound to the intent of what the user, community, or organization wants to achieve with the data. For better use with standard tools and to be shared among others, understood, and used correctly, it is good practice to define a set of standard processes to promote good data quality and maximize the value that can be extracted and used, and reused in strategic and significant activities (research, business tasks, visions, etc.).
Researcher level	Enhanced researcher skills in data retention requirements are necessary for promoting research collaboration and sharing of best practices. Having a common understanding of technical vocabulary and practices helps to avoid confusion and lost time. Investing in researcher skills related to data retention enhances the reuse of research data.
Knowledge-loss through retirement, attrition or temporary contracts.	Many RPOs are lacking clear policies for retaining data when a researcher is either retiring or leaving for another organisation. Similarly, projects that have been done on temporary funding may become “orphans” and there is uncertainty about the responsibility. RPO’s need to make sure that the processes of retiring and changing jobs take into consideration data legacy in terms of their quality and value. Project data left unattended risks becoming obsolete due to a lack of documentation

4.2.2 Recommendations

To address the various challenges posed by a lack of expertise in data retention, here are some recommended practices.

- **Increase awareness among researchers about the importance of data retention.**
 - Develop strategies and guidelines to encourage organizations and institutions to support and promote the work of future researchers by embedding data retention and stewardship practices into everyday research workflows. Every step, study, and result contributes to a cumulative chain of knowledge, and sustained institutional support is essential to preserving expertise and enabling significant discoveries..
 - Ensure that the quality of research data is recognized and valued alongside the final published paper.
 - Promote the idea of open data sharing, the value of clear, sustainable governance of datasets and data retention in supporting current and future research.

- RPO's managers need to recognize whether and when to invest in skills, infrastructure, and inter-institutional institutions.
- **Building skills in workflows, data documentation, and specialized expertise**
 - Specify flows and rules for the life cycle of the data, and help identify what and in which format to maintain and store the data
 - Identify people or departments with the needed skills and start a collaboration
 - If the skills are not already present in the organization or institution, and new employees cannot be hired, find out who can start building such a skill, and/or start a collaboration with other institutions
 - Build a well-connected network of data stewards, experts in the different departments
 - Collaboration between different data stewards to promote the building of a repository infrastructure.
 - Define a common Data Retention Plan
 - Define and publish policies and best practices
 - Help users to better plan their research data retention for future uses
- **Set up well-defined processes**
 - Institutions need well-defined processes for when a researcher retires or leaves, specifying who will assume responsibility for the research and its data, and deciding whether the work should be continued or concluded.
- **Recognition of the importance of data security**
 - Ensuring the institution recognizes the importance of protecting data and controlling access. Prioritize the implementation of essential security practices.

Challenge 3: Discipline and content-specific challenges

4.3.1 Description of the challenge

The disciplinary challenges of data retention span over a wide range of issues which we grouped into two categories: cross-disciplinary challenges that are common across fields, and discipline-specific challenges that are unique to particular research domains.

Cross-disciplinary challenges

Data retention faces cross-disciplinary challenges due to wide variations in data types, formats, retention requirements, preservation practices, and levels of awareness. Some common challenges include incomplete metadata, inconsistent documentation standards, limited support for sensitive and indigenous data, and a lack of robust strategies for reassessing legacy datasets (Andreassen et al., 2025a). Furthermore, many repositories operate without formal exit plans or long-term sustainability frameworks, raising concerns about their durability and continuity. Repositories also exhibit significant variation in terms of maturity, documentation quality, and available support services. While some are well-established, backed by comprehensive policies and robust infrastructure, others—particularly smaller initiatives—struggle to implement and sustain standards for long-term digital preservation and data quality.

- **Different retention requirements.** Different research disciplines and content types have vastly different requirements for data retention, preservation formats, and access protocols, creating a fragmented landscape of incompatible standards across European repositories (Mohr et al., 2015). Conflicting policies that are varied across funders, institutions, subject domains and with differing national standards lead to inconsistencies in retention requirements. This makes it difficult to work across boundaries and can lead to confusion for researchers, especially when open science mandates are linked to different legal and ethical obligations. This complexity is compounded by the evolving nature of policies, which introduces uncertainty for long-term planning and compliance.
- **Distinct preservation practices.** Different disciplines have developed their own data preservation practices. For example, life sciences may need to keep data for decades for longitudinal studies, while the humanities often require indefinite preservation for cultural heritage. These efforts are further complicated by overlapping regulations that can sometimes conflict, such as clinical trial rules versus GDPR's data minimization requirements.
- **Awareness of retention regulations.** Awareness of regulations regarding data retention from governments or institutions' standards also varies across different disciplines, leading to discrepancies in how data preservation obligations are understood and applied. Some disciplines lack a clear consensus on optimal

retention periods, while others are constrained by inflexible regulatory requirements that don't always account for evolving research practices.

- **Distinct technical requirements across content types.** Different data types and formats require distinct technical support, e.g., genomic data needs specialized computational environments, cultural heritage datasets require 3D visualization (Champion & Rahaman, 2020; Quantin et al., 2023), and social science surveys demand statistical software compatibility.
- **Determining appropriate retention periods.** Determining appropriate retention periods becomes contentious when balancing legal minimums, scientific value, storage costs, and ethical considerations. This fragmentation creates significant barriers for interdisciplinary research that increasingly requires data integration across fields with incompatible preservation standards.
- **Limited understanding of the data value.** Domain experts and the scientific community often know which data is valuable to keep, the required retention periods, and any special handling or preservation needs. Technical teams often rely on the scientific community and domain experts to implement preservation strategies. This creates a dependency that may lead to gaps if communication is unclear, incomplete or discontinued.
- **Limited recognition of the importance of data preservation.** Scientific communities often underestimate the importance of data preservation both within their own disciplines and in relation to other fields, leading to insufficient community consensus on defining core metadata for preservation and inadequate appreciation of cross-disciplinary data value.

Within-disciplinary challenges

There are challenges even within the same discipline, as the data type could vary among different studies/projects, and defining the core data to preserve needs community consensus, which is now often underestimated by the scientific community.

Life Sciences - big data volume to retain for long periods (time duration is a significant matter in this case, considering the cost), sensitive data (but certain phenotype data are important), privacy and GDPR, and specialized data types (e.g., medical images, genomics files) evolve quickly. For example, one major challenge in data retention in some Life Science projects is the large size of image files, often ranging from 100 GB to 10 TB or more, requiring either high-speed internet for transfer or physical transport via external drives for long-term storage and access (Bajcsy et al., 2025). Despite ethical

concerns over the use of animals in research, promoting the re-use of animal research data, there is a poor outlook for animal data re-use. Recent studies show that approximately 50% of animal experiments never publish any data (Bjerke, 2024). If animal use regulations at the European level become exceedingly more strict, having high-quality, accessible, and reusable animal data will become essential for various fields of research in the Life Sciences.

Humanities and Social Sciences - challenges related to awareness regarding data preservation requirements, standards, solutions, diverse formats, context-dependent metadata, and complex ethical and legal considerations due to sometimes complex data ownership (Gualandi et al., 2022). Also, preservation challenges arise due to heterogeneous digital representations and the complex stratification of metadata across multiple representation levels. A critical challenge involves preserving specialized interfaces and interactive systems, such as digital critical editions that link textual analysis to physical manuscript reproductions and apographs, where the preservation of functional relationships and navigational structures is as important as the underlying data. Many social sciences, encompassing political science, economics, psychology, and business studies, encounter different preservation challenges centered on privacy, confidentiality, and temporal sensitivity of human-centered data. These fields often derive scientific value from longitudinal analysis spanning decades, creating tensions between privacy protection requirements and the need for long-term accessibility for policy evaluation and trend analysis (CESSDA Training Team, 2020). The interdisciplinary nature of certain fields and the multitude of different stakeholders involved in Cultural Heritage custody (libraries, museums, archives, galleries, universities, and research institutions, both private and public) create difficulties in establishing unified preservation standards across archaeology, art history, anthropology, and digital humanities.

Cultural heritage - Specialized cultural heritage file formats often lack long-term sustainability pathways, while retention periods are particularly challenging as materials typically require indefinite preservation due to their irreplaceable nature, creating significant storage costs. For example, a painting requires metadata about the original artwork, its photographic reproduction (lighting, camera settings, date), the digitization of that photograph, and potentially its inclusion within 3D reconstructions of exhibition spaces, each layer demanding specific technical and contextual metadata. Additionally, complex intellectual property rights and cultural heritage protection laws, indigenous knowledge protocols, and community consent issues restrict preservation options, compounded by dynamic provenance and rights information that changes over time.

Political and Economics - Data in these domains may be subject to classification levels, declassification schedules, and commercial sensitivity that change over time, while psychological research involving human subjects requires robust anonymization and consent management.

Natural Sciences - Data related to natural sciences often comes from observational studies, experimental studies, and a large amount of calculations and modeling. The appropriate retention period for such data varies depending on the type collected and its long-term value for research and reproducibility. A key challenge lies in the diversity of data types and structures, and sometimes it is not only the scientific data itself that requires preservation, but also accompanying contextual or administrative information. For instance, the preservation effort at CERN involves far more than just experimental data (Data Preservation, 2025). As of early 2019, CERN had generated approximately 420 petabytes (420 million gigabytes) of data from past and ongoing high-energy physics experiments. Physical sciences, including physics, chemistry, and mathematics, face technical complexity in preserving large-scale experimental data from specialized instrumentation, computational models requiring specific software environments, and the need to maintain calibration metadata essential for data interpretation (ESCAPE, n.d.).

Technology - In the fields of Computer science, information technology, and engineering, unique data preservation challenges are rising due to rapid technological evolution and diverse data ecosystems (Corrado, 2022). Technical obsolescence occurs rapidly in technology domains, where software, hardware platforms, and data formats evolve continuously, creating preservation challenges when essential computational environments and dependencies become unavailable. Reproducibility in computational research requires preserving not only the data but also the complete software stack, including source code, dependencies, and computational environments, as software is increasingly recognized as a critical research artifact. Engineering disciplines face particular challenges in preserving the social context and decision-making processes behind product data, as technical documentation must capture not just the final outputs but also the collaborative knowledge and rationale that informed design choices. Additionally, intellectual property constraints and complex licensing agreements often limit preservation options for proprietary software and data formats.

Agriculture - Precision agriculture and agri-tech represent an emerging technological domain with distinct preservation requirements driven by IoT sensor networks and real-time data streams. Agricultural IoT systems generate continuous data from diverse sensors monitoring soil conditions, weather parameters, crop health, and livestock

behavior, requiring specialized storage architectures capable of handling high-velocity, heterogeneous data streams. The sector faces implementation challenges, including high costs, data security concerns, and the need for digital literacy among agricultural practitioners (Digitalising the EU Agricultural Sector | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future, n.d.). Critical scientific challenges emerge from the need to integrate multiple types of sensory data over time and translate complex analytical outputs into actionable farming decisions, requiring preservation of both raw sensor data and the analytical models used for decision support. Geospatial precision is fundamental, as agricultural data is inherently location-dependent, and climate change impacts create additional urgency for long-term environmental monitoring and trend analysis. Government initiatives recognize the strategic importance of precision agriculture data, with substantial federal investments in research and development highlighting the need for coordinated preservation strategies.

4.3.2 Recommendations

To address disciplinary challenges and their specific requirements in digital preservation, we propose solutions such as developing discipline-specific preservation profiles, documenting dependencies, specifying recommended retention time, etc. See Table 2 for detailed information on the proposed solutions addressing key challenges and the corresponding stakeholders involved. Some solutions may also apply to other challenges.

Table 2 Key Challenges and Proposed Solutions for Discipline- and Content-Specific Requirements and Implementation in Long-Term Data Retention

Key Challenges	Proposed Solutions	Key Stakeholders
Within-disciplinary challenges		
Vast difference in requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Developing a discipline-specific preservation profile B. Specifying recommended retention times and triggers for re-appraisal 	Scientific communities, researchers, data stewards and curators
Unequal awareness of preservation importance and practices within the discipline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C. Raise awareness and foster knowledge exchange D. Developing targeted training initiatives and community guidelines 	Institutional policymakers, International organizations and initiatives focused on digital preservation

Distinct preservation practices	E. Encourage community-driven governance.	Discipline-specific working groups, incl. researchers, repository managers, and policymakers, european repository network
Cross-disciplinary challenges		
Technical requirements vary across content types	F. Flexible storage and preservation solutions G. Develop technical standards and APIs	Data infrastructure, Service provider, data stewards and curators
Underestimating the importance of data preservation relative to other disciplines	H. Improve the awareness of data stewards and researchers. I. Share a transparent disciplinary profile J. Institutional specialization.	Policymakers, scientific communities, researchers and domain experts, data stewards, repository managers
Retention Time Disparities	K. Determining appropriate retention periods	Legal and compliance officers, institutional policymakers, data curators, repository administrators

The following provides detailed information on each proposed solution:

- A. **Develop discipline-specific preservation profiles that align with domain-specific data types, formats, metadata, and workflows.** Create standardized but adaptable preservation profiles for major research disciplines, developed through consultation with disciplinary communities, professional associations, and regulatory bodies. These profiles should define minimum metadata requirements, preferred file formats, retention periods, and access protocols while allowing institutional flexibility.
- B. **Specify recommended retention times and re-appraisal triggers for different disciplines.** Specifying recommended retention times and defining discipline-specific re-appraisal triggers ensures that digital assets remain relevant, accessible, and cost-efficient over time. Establishing clear guidelines not only supports compliance with ethical and legal requirements but also helps institutions make informed decisions about storage, curation, and eventual deaccessioning. Regular re-appraisal cycles

further guarantee that preservation strategies adapt to evolving scientific priorities, technological changes, and community needs.

- C. **Raise Awareness and Foster Knowledge Exchange.** Ensure that data stewards and support specialists are aware of disciplinary differences in data practices, and promote knowledge exchange to strengthen their capacity to support tailored preservation strategies.
- D. **Developing targeted training initiatives and community guidelines** to raise awareness of data stewardship across subfields within and across the disciplines. Mandatory training at the graduate level on retention needs. Policy at the institutional level.
- E. **Foster community-driven governance**, by establishing discipline-specific working groups within the European repository network that bring together researchers, repository managers, and policymakers to develop practical, sustainable preservation solutions, to ensure practical and sustainable solutions. These working groups should continuously refine preservation requirements based on evolving research practices, technological capabilities, and regulatory changes. In the Arts and Humanities domain, DARIAH is trying to support digital research infrastructure through community-driven governance (DARIAH-DE, 2017; Tóth-Czifra, 2019).
- F. **Implement a flexible storage and preservation solution** that 1) handles diverse file formats, software dependency issues, access modes, and data sensitivity levels; 2) is linked to retention schedules and re-appraisal.
- G. **Develop technical standards and APIs** that enable data discovery and integration across disciplinary boundaries, focusing on common metadata schemas, persistent identifier systems, and format migration pathways that preserve semantic meaning across different research contexts.
- H. **Improve the awareness of data stewards and researchers.** Especially those of principal investigators, scientific communities and consortia, as they could lead or initiate the projects and keep searching for funding to support the transition from temporary data storage to long-term data retention. Foster community-driven governance and more training and workshops in this regard. Provide available resources and easy access. Encourage researchers or data creators to draft comprehensive retention and appraisal plans as part of DMPs, aligning with FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016a). Encourage them to describe how long data will be kept, the reasons, and when and how it will be deleted or archived, especially

the specific needs based on community standards and policy, and the nature.

- I. **Sharing a transparent disciplinary profile and promoting open sharing of preservation practices** helps improve data collaboration and reuse. Encouraging bottom-up knowledge sharing across disciplines fosters community engagement and supports the development of flexible, interoperable preservation solutions.
- J. **Institutional specialization.** Development of discipline-specific centers of excellence within the EU network, where institutions can develop deep expertise in particular content types while sharing transversal knowledge.
- K. **Determining appropriate retention periods.** A balanced approach should be adopted to determine appropriate retention periods, integrating legal requirements, scientific value assessments, cost-effectiveness, and ethical and environmental considerations. This approach ensures data is retained long enough to maximize research benefits while minimizing unnecessary storage and respecting ethical and sustainability principles.

Challenge 4: Lack of standards, guidelines and policies

4.4.1 Description of the challenge

In the domain of research data management, while data retention guidelines exist – driven by funders, legal requirements, ethics, and institutional RDM policies – standards for reappraisal and clarity for what happens after mandated retention periods end remain rare. The challenge lies not in the initial retention phase, but in the transition from active RDM to long term archiving once the retention clock runs out. Decisions about whether to preserve data beyond mandated periods or to delete them are often driven more by cost and effort constraints on the part of data providers than by established internal policies or institutional strategies for post retention management. This lack of structured guidance for the post-retention phase leaves significant gaps that undermine both the long-term value and accessibility of scientific data. A useful perspective can be drawn from classical archival theory, which assesses the value of archival objects through multiple lenses:

- **Primary Value:** The original purpose for which records were created—within research, this aligns with the immediate scientific objectives and needs of the community.
- **Secondary Value:** The potential for re-use in different contexts or disciplines—scientific data may have applications beyond their initial field or purpose.

- **Evidential Value:** The capacity of records to document the functions and activities of their creators—research data can serve to validate methodologies or institutional practices.
- **Informational Value:** The content-based usefulness of data, independent of its origin or context—such as datasets used for modeling, comparative studies, or long-term observational analyses.

The challenge lies in the translation of these archival principles to the scientific data in general and the adaptation to discipline specific needs. Recent work, such as that from EDEN Work Package 3 (Andreassen et al., 2025a), has highlighted the lack of long-term preservation (LTP) policies and reappraisal strategies in scientific domains, particularly for managing data beyond mandated retention periods.

A major barrier to sustainable reappraisal and deletion practices is the limited awareness among data providers, users, and funders about post retention responsibilities. Long-term preservation beyond the project funded period often lacks dedicated financial backing. This raises a crucial question: who bears the cost of long-term data preservation after mandatory retention periods expire? Conflicting policies that are varied across funders, institutions, subject domains, and with differing national standards lead to inconsistencies in post-retention requirements. This makes it difficult to work across boundaries and can lead to confusion for researchers, especially when open science mandates are linked to different legal and ethical obligations regarding data lifecycle management. The situation becomes even more complex as policies evolve. Without mechanisms to monitor policy changes and, especially, without efforts to align them where possible, the barriers for researchers only continue to grow.

Policies change over time, and the lack of oversight of these policies is currently a key obstacle to shared management at the national/international level and often in specific sectors when considering the interoperability of data management technologies and concepts. The lack of policy clarity regarding post retention data management is also problematic. Transparency is crucial for understanding the conflicting policies among different funders, institutions, and other stakeholders.

4.4.2 Recommendations

A few initiatives are addressing this challenge regarding defining preservation practices and improving the network for the trustworthy repositories, such as the Nestor Working Group on Archival Standards for Research Data, and the EOSC projects like EDEN and FIDELIS. In EOSC EDEN, Core Preservation Processes (CPPs) are identified (EOSC EDEN et al., 2025),

specific actions that every Trustworthy Digital Archive should undertake adequately - either directly or through its associated parties or services, in order to fulfill its digital preservation missions as evidenced in its preservation policy. The FIDELIS Matrix (TTRAM) of the FIDELIS project has been designed to better understand repositories, and how transparency around the broad range of activities and functions they undertake can contribute to trustworthiness (L'Hours et al., 2025).

Standards for reappraisal are increasingly being incorporated into certification frameworks, such as CoreTrustSeal (CTS) and NestorSeal, enhancing trust and transparency in data management practices. Regarding data deletion, only a few guidelines exist, like (Anders et al., 2024), which helps to decide between retention or deletion.

Although these initiatives aim to improve the trustworthiness of established repositories via transparency of preservation practices, it remains unclear how well they'll be able to address the assessment point that occurs when a digital object's retention period has expired. This topic is touched upon by the Long Term Data Retention Task Force's paper on a "conceptual framework for the implementation of the Retention, (Re)Reappraisal - Iterative Logic (RRAIL)"⁷.

Challenge 5: Understanding the value of data holdings

4.5.1 Description of the challenge

The following describes several challenges in understanding the value of data.

- Lack of data valuing techniques. One of the causes is that data value has many dimensions (e.g., business utility, impact, timeliness), yet there is uncertainty about which data value dimensions to include in a value assessment. Moreover, there is a lot of overlap between data value and data quality dimensions (Brennan et al., 2019).
- Missing or incomplete information about data assets leads to flawed discovery processes and an inability to reuse the data effectively. Although it is commonly understood that (at least initially) the creator of a data set is the primary beneficiary when it comes to data that has been deposited in a repository, storage system or digital preservation system, the long tail of the data management life cycle will often lead to a situation where the benefits realised by secondary users gradually overtake those derived by the creator. This inevitably leads to a situation where the persons

⁷ The delivery report, "Conceptual framework on the implementation of workflows concerning Retention (Re) Appraisal - Iteration Logic (RRAIL)" will be published concurrently with this document.

using the data are deriving the majority of the benefit and incurring none of the costs. Funding digital preservation solutions is “for the good of the community”, but it can be difficult to make the case when cost and benefit centres don’t align.

- Funding issues. Many funding regimens only fund processes that occur during the lifetime of a project. The majority of the costs associated with digital preservation occur after the end of a project (Kejser et al., 2011).
- Imbalance of cost-benefit analysis. The costs of producing research data are generally easier to quantify (in monetary terms) compared to the benefits. Benefits may be very scattered, and they may not materialise until after a considerable time lag.
- The heterogeneity of data assets. Research performing organisations (RPO) can harbor research data holdings that are considered as private assets. Such data holdings may be protected by intellectual property licensing enabling the translation of research into commercial value, via e.g. a university technology transfer office. At the same time, a large proportion of the research data holdings of RPOs are usually set to be openly available to the general public in line with the guiding principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” (Nogueira et al., 2024). In addition, some data holdings may fall between these two scenarios, for example, research software can be given a dual-license enabling research use on the one hand and commercial distribution on the other. Taken together, the research data holdings of many RPOs can be considered to consist of holdings with market value (i.e. economic/business value) and those with non-market value (i.e., societal or scientific value). RPO’s need, therefore, to balance their research data governance so that it accommodates the needs of both types of data holdings.
- Data life cycle. The research data holdings of RPO’s may also consist of raw, unprocessed data and curated, derived data that has gone through varying degrees of processing or transformations. Raw data can be more robust in suiting various use cases, while curated, derived data suits specific purposes. Hence, the value of research data is influenced also by its maturity, i.e. its stage in the data life cycle. Curating and storing data is costly. In valuing data holdings, RPOs need to account for the costs of research data curation in order to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Data can be findable, yet unusable due to missing documentation and contextual information, hence diminishing reuse value. In addition, the reuse value of a dataset may also depend on the format used.

- Value vs volume. In valuing data assets, what is the relationship between the “amount” of data and its value? Value may be derived from big data and smaller datasets in different ways (Werner et al., 2023).
- Impact vs value. Universities often focus on measuring *impact*, but how does this relate to *value*? According to Brennan et al. (2019), *impact* is one of several dimensions that contribute to data value, alongside factors such as business utility and other contextual considerations.

4.5.2 Recommendations

Missing information about data assets could be alleviated by investing in an institutional data catalogue, also by harnessing DMPs more efficiently. Involving appropriate stakeholders - such as the technology transfer or innovation office, scientists, legal team, and IT department - could also be helpful. However, this requires a clear understanding of the costs associated with data retention, curation and related activities, in relation to their potential market, social, or scientific value.

Developing research data governance models within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) is essential to ensure that governance frameworks take into account the organisation’s data assets—both from an open science perspective and in terms of commercialisation potential (Nogueira et al., 2024). Effective research data governance can enhance the value of research data holdings by managing them strategically. While the focus is often placed on the value and volume of big data, RPOs also need to recognise the utility and value of smaller, high-quality datasets. For example, the costs of data retention and curation are generally lower for small datasets.

Below are a few examples that relate to understanding the data value.

- A university evaluation guide for datasets going to long-term preservation (Fairdata-PAS): “Digital Preservation (Fairdata-PAS): Guidelines for UH Evaluators” (Talvinen, 2019).
- The Data Value Map: A framework for developing shared understanding on data initiatives (Nagle & Sammon, 2017)
- A study used five major data value dimensions from 20 organisations ranging from finance to aviation: operational impact (utility), dataset replacement costs, competitive advantage (market value), regulatory risk, and timeliness (Brennan et al., 2019).

Challenge 6: Technological challenges

4.6.1 Description of the challenge

Technology is at the core of the challenges which long-term data retention face. Technological challenges therefore exist at many levels. Within the scope of this report, we have collected different challenges and mapped them against three levels: the infrastructure itself, the interoperability between the single infrastructures and the data itself. These primary levels describe where the challenge occurs. A second mapping for each challenge is conducted against the vectors data volume, information content, inter-organisational, intra-organisational, preservation awareness and technological change. These vectors describe the main driver or reason behind the challenge. Intra-organisational describes organisation specific barriers such as lack of resources, lack of knowledge or lack of institutional buy-in which hinder a technological implementation. In the cases of consortia or service-based setups as well as in all cases of interoperability, intra-organisational challenges often result in inter-organisational challenges. In other cases, inter-organisational challenges exist when an agreement between institutional players cannot be reached. A lack of preservation awareness is often at the root of both, inter- and intra-organisational challenges. The vector *preservation awareness* describes the situation where standard processes, frameworks and guidelines exist, but are not leveraged by an institution or community. We also recognize that specific types of data or technological implementations pose challenges. The vector *data volume* flags challenges where handling the growth of data is at the root of the challenge. The vector *information content* flags challenges where the type of information or data stored poses a specific challenge. Lastly, the vector *technological change* flags those challenges, where the rapid development of technology is at the root.

Technological challenges on an infrastructure level

Infrastructure describes an implementation of hard- / software (including network, storage) found within a single institution or shared by several institutions in a consortia or service-based manner. Technological challenges collected at that level are as follows:

- organizations have different technological implementations of systems based on their financial funds/resources but also based on the expectations and needs of their stakeholders (e.g., based on required data size, interaction with the data, data complexity)
vectors: intra-organisational
- growth / renewal of technological implementations will most likely not be homogenous but continuously widen the gap between different single infrastructures

(based on e.g. availability of additional national funding but also based on institutional capabilities)

vectors: data volume; intra-organisational; inter-organisational

- constant risk of used technologies becoming obsolete / technologies disappearing (e.g., constant discussion on the longevity of the tape storage market)
vectors: technological change
- notion of storing the data in a living system as opposed to “preserving media” and discussing technological obsolescence
vectors: technological change; preservation awareness; inter-organisational
- operating data repositories as an infrastructure instead of running separate instances by individual organisations/data producers
vectors: inter-organisational; intra-organisational
- computing centres lack long-term preservation policies are often allocated “in-kind” as part of the compute time allocation
vectors: preservation awareness
- data transfer across borders is sometimes slow due to wrong routing policies between national and international networks, despite having very high bandwidth connectivity available
vectors: intra-organisational
- data-specific requirements for cyber security of the preserved content exist, e.g. cyber security must be at the highest level when it contains classified / sensitive information
vectors: information content
- lack of guidelines to steer storage policies for temporary archive versus final archive: how to select content candidate for cold storage?
vectors: preservation awareness; data volume; information content
- a data handling policy within the organisation or within a shared infrastructure may be difficult or costly to implement
vectors: inter-organisational; intra-organisational; information content
- criteria to outsource an infrastructure into the Cloud are not available, hard to implement and/or face significant push-back on an organisational level despite high

risks and costs associated with on-premises solutions
vectors: inter-organisational; data volume; technological change

- ensure bit preservation with a redundant infrastructure is often seen as too costly / not implementable
vectors: preservation awareness; inter-organisational; data volume
- for many infrastructural implementations long-term risks are not considered
vectors: preservation awareness; technological change

The most frequent vectors of the infrastructure levels collected are inter-organisational (6), intra-organisational (5) and preservation awareness (5). This hints at two things: Organisations are facing these challenges due to a lack of resources and organisations are facing these challenges due to a lack of knowledge in the form of existing frameworks, guidelines, policies.

Technological challenges on an interoperability level

Interoperability describes the capability of a system or product to interact and function with others. This includes the seamless communication between different technological infrastructures, e.g. in the form of well-documented web services as well as the ability to exchange and use information without the use of web services. The latter requires well documented structures to allow the interpretation by others.

- Research data is stored in a technologically fragmented landscape, which makes it not only challenging to locate data but also results in different levels of data representation and documentation
vectors: inter-organisational; preservation awareness
- lack of interoperability of systems between each other due to lack of shared communication protocols (e.g. APIs) and standardized data exchange (e.g. formats)
vectors: inter-organisational; preservation awareness
- for sensitive data, a lack of standard procedures for access control—e.g., with regards to access committees—poses a major issue
vectors: information content; inter-organisational
- Object storage is often implemented by subset of S3 specification which itself does not have its own RFC or IEEE standard
vectors: inter-organisational; intra-organisational; preservation awareness

- Despite the widespread use of modern web-based AAI such as OAuth 2.0, no common solution for enforcing data access rights exists
vectors: information content

As expected for interoperability, the inter-organisational vector is at the core of the majority of the challenges collected (4). This is closely followed by preservation awareness (3) meaning that standard processes, frameworks and guidelines exist but are not leveraged by an institution or community.

Technological challenges on the data level

- lack of interoperability for dispersed systems that cannot interact directly per design / mission (e.g., for highly sensitive data systems cannot be interlinked, instead an offline-method to enable interoperability needs to be found)
vectors: information content; inter-organisational
- the challenge of technological change itself and with that the changing expectations in how the user interacts with / re-uses the data needs to be integrated into any long-term retention and preservation workflows; it requires an ongoing re-evaluation of the data's format as well as suitable software to allow for data interaction; these requirements may be highly discipline-specific to the point where an older file format may not be considered useable by one discipline while it's still in use by another
vectors: preservation awareness; technological change

With only two challenges collected at the data level, vector trends cannot be detected. However, it is notable that one of these two challenges is related to sensitive data, which is a specific *information content* use case that was also mentioned on the interoperability and infrastructural levels.

4.6.2 Recommendations

While the above listed generic trends for technological challenges exist, it is important to consider their impact on a discipline-, organisation type and even institution specific level (Andreassen et al., 2025b). The vector trends across all three levels showed, however, that a major gap does not necessarily exist in the general availability of technology to handle data with regards to growing volume or complexity, but rather in the organisational resources and awareness to implement that technology. Two exceptions to this are the handling of sensitive data, which was flagged as problematic on all levels, and redundant bitstream preservation for large data volumes.

The lack of organisational resources on a financial level can only be met by ongoing and future EU and national investments into research information infrastructure. Project-based funding here stands in stark contrast to the need of funding for long-term data preservation infrastructures, for which a clear way of funding needs to be established. This is expanded on further in Challenge 1 “Lack of funding”.

For the lack of preservation awareness in connection to technology, much work remains to be done to integrate preservation technology into research information infrastructures. While many projects build on the generic data-focused FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016b), few of those addressed infrastructural needs for long-term data retention and preservation. The TRUST principles (Lin et al., 2020a) outline high-level institutional responsibilities to meet these needs, but are far too broad to function as a concrete framework to address the gaps outlined in this paper.

At the infrastructural level an improved categorization of organisational implementations has been introduced in form of the CoreTrustSeal LoRCAP (Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation) classification (L’Hours et al., 2024). In addition, the EOSC EDEN project has identified and described Core Preservation Processes (CPP) as specific actions that every trustworthy digital archive should undertake adequately - either directly or through its associated parties or services (EOSC EDEN et al., 2025). Implementation of processes and guidelines like LoRCAP and CPP at an infrastructural level also enhance interoperability between institutions and infrastructures. For the repository side, the EOSC FIDELIS project has recently published the FIDELIS TTRAMatrix (Transparent, Trustworthy Attributes Matrix), which will link out to EDEN CPP in a forthcoming version (L’Hours et al., 2025). Additional efforts that address specific gaps in these areas are information package specifications such as E-ARK CSIP (Common Specification for Information Packages) or potentially the forthcoming OAI-IF (Open Archival Information System - Interoperability Framework) (Kearney et al., 2025). At the data level, technological challenges are partly addressed in the aforementioned EOSC EDEN CPPs as well as in EOSC EDEN forthcoming work around the re-use fitness model (EDEN-FIDELIS, 2025). While these processes need to be adapted for each new content type on the granularity level of file formats and data structures, the (re-)appraisal of the data for long-term retention and active digital preservation requires not only technical infrastructure but also skill and expertise. Within the scope of this challenge chapter, it is therefore mainly allocated at the infrastructural level. Further work on re-appraisal is outlined and discussed in detail in the EOSC TF paper on “Retention (Re-)Appraisal - Reiteration Logic” and will be driven in the scope of the EOSC FIDELIS and EDEN projects.

Challenge 7: Legal challenges

4.7.1 Description of the challenge

Legal differences

In Europe, organizations face various challenges complying to laws or regulations in the context of data retention. Whether from a legal, technical, or operational perspective, they encounter the complexity of regulatory frameworks that differ from country to country and are constantly evolving. The main challenge when it comes to laws, regulations, and rules that must be applied to certain types of data is to clearly define which categories of data are subject to measures that apply to so-called sensitive and/or high-risk data. Personally identifiable information, financial or medical data, or any data that could compromise the safety of a citizen, must be subject to protection.

Sensitive data is already subject to specific legal regulations at both European and national levels. These laws generally define how such data must be handled, who is allowed to use it, and under what conditions. However, applying these regulations is not straightforward. Many of the rules leave room for interpretation and are flexible, or the same regulation may be applied differently from one country to another. This makes it difficult to establish a consistent and universal approach across Europe.

A clear example is how the GDPR defines the maximum period of time personal data can be retained. The regulation does not specify exact retention duration for each category of data; it simply states that data must be kept only *for as long as necessary*. The maximum retention period may vary significantly between these categories.

These regulations become challenging to manage when the same category of data must be transferred from one country to another, where similar legal frameworks may conflict in their practical implementation. For the same category of data, such as medical records, some countries require their deletion after ten years, while others mandate their retention for potential reuse in research and/or analytical purposes. The same applies to financial data: in certain jurisdictions, the objective is to delete the data as soon as the legally mandated retention period expires, in order to reduce the risk of unauthorized access or misuse. In other countries, however, regulations may require indefinite retention to ensure availability for future reference or legal proceedings.

In the specific context of data retention, establishing harmonized rules applicable to a wide range of data types and mutually recognized across different countries remains a complex and unresolved challenge among EU member states.

In the field of data protection and applicable regulations, Europe faces a significant overlap of EU regulations, directives, and national laws. Alongside the GDPR, which aimed to harmonize data protection across member states, new legislative acts have been introduced over the years to address emerging needs driven by technological evolution, the continuous and global exchange of data, and the rise of artificial intelligence. These include the AI Act (Artificial Intelligence Act), the Digital Services Act (DSA), the Data Governance Act (DGA), the European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS) and many others.

Each of these acts or regulations seek to address various facets of emerging practices or technologies, with the aim of minimizing the risk of harm to individuals through the misuse of their sensitive data.

This layering of legal instruments, each responding to a distinct and contextualized need, adds further complexity, creating uncertainty and challenges in achieving consistent and compliant implementation across complex and international environments.

The coexistence of laws and regulations defined by different countries and jurisdictions can challenge the very notion of data sovereignty. For example, the GDPR requires that personal data of EU citizens be protected from unauthorized access and that any transfer to third parties must be based on a valid and existing legal framework. This requirement is in direct conflict with the Cloud Act (Clarifying Lawful Overseas Use of Data Act), which allows U.S. authorities to request access to data held by U.S. companies operating in Europe, without informing the users or involving European authorities.

The concept of data sovereignty must be further reinforced through a combination of legal, technical, and contractual strategies, such as:

- Preferably using European cloud providers that are not headquartered in countries where the application of international regulations is unclear or potentially conflicting with the sovereignty of the data.
- For highly sensitive data, implementing encryption practices where the decryption key is stored locally within Europe.
- Establishing clear contracts with cloud providers that ensure European regulations are fully respected and not overridden by non-compliant requests from third-country authorities.

Given the significant complexity of today's regulatory and legislative landscape, organizations and users often struggle to understand which law or regulation they have to apply. It is therefore essential for organizations to rely on qualified experts and consultants to

help define and implement internal rules and procedures that are both clear to users and fully compliant with current legislation.

At the same time, at the European level, it is necessary to bring forward concrete and applicable solutions that can support organizations, individual users, and researchers. One example of an effort to clarify and address the difficulties researchers face in actually accessing open data is the project launched by the European Commission: LIBER (Action Plan on Improving Access and Reuse of Research Results, (van der Graaf et al., 2025). This initiative aims to tackle the challenges researchers encounter when trying to access and reuse data, materials, and results from other research projects.

Data sovereignty

Digital sovereignty in research data is the ability of research institutions to *retain control* over their data assets, ensuring compliance with legal frameworks, ethical considerations, and operational best practices. For European research institutions digital sovereignty is essential to maintain trust, ensure long-term accessibility, and balance openness while maintaining a responsible data governance.

Data sovereignty also depends on well-defined agreements regarding data ownership, licensing, and re-use. Research data often evolves from primary datasets into derived or synthetic datasets, requiring careful governance. It can also contribute in major parts to commercial products, either through direct further development or through indirect methods such as license changes (Gallese, 2024).

Operational Control

Beyond ethical concerns, sovereignty also depends on adopting recognized data governance frameworks like the FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016a), TRUST (Lin et al., 2020b) and CARE principles (Carroll et al., 2020).

By integrating these principles, institutions can preserve sovereignty while promoting responsible data sharing. These principles also continue to apply when dealing with restricted data records, whether these are protected by data protection or sovereign requirements.

A critical but often overlooked aspect of digital sovereignty is ensuring that research data remains accessible and usable over time. While e.g. the TRUST principles already consider this aspect we want to emphasise them explicitly :

- A clear definition of responsibility for long-term preservation (individual researchers, institutions, national repositories).
- A fall-back mechanism if storage providers, infrastructures or the socio-political environment change (e.g., data migration plans, redundancy strategies).
- A stable financial sustainability plan, avoiding reliance on short-term project funding.

Digital sovereignty in research data requires a multi-layered approach, integrating legal compliance, ethical governance, operational control, and technical resilience. Ultimately, sovereignty should empower researchers, ensuring that data remains a public good, accessible and reusable under transparent and fair conditions.

4.7.2 Recommendations

To mitigate long-term risks according to national and European Data Protection laws and to further secure scientific data against unexpected and difficult to predict misuse cases, research institutions should prioritize open and interoperable European cloud infrastructures and establish data governance agreements that prevent unauthorized access or jurisdictional conflicts, also see Table 3.

Institutions should ensure that

- Primary data remains accessible and trackable throughout its lifecycle, i.e.:
 - Ensuring persistent accessibility, regularly evaluating and avoiding or reducing reliance on external third parties.
 - Keeping an inventory of published critical data sets and monitoring of re-use and re-propagation trends
- Re-use and re-propagation of data are governed by clear licensing and attribution rules:
 - Consequent application of licensing frameworks (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data Commons, or if unavoidable bespoke institutional licenses) to define clear usage rights.
 - Continuous development of a strategy and workflow to deal with potential usage cases not aligned with institutional policies
 - A shift of responsibility for the selection of an applicable framework from the individual scientist to a dedicated higher-level authority within the institution.

- Legal and technical tools and their enforcement are considered to be used when necessary to protect sensitive datasets. These could encompass non-disclosure agreements (NDAs), re-utilisation contracts and might be flanked in specific cases by technical solutions.⁸

Institutions should implement

- Ethical Risk Assessment Frameworks to evaluate when usage constraints are necessary.
- A Technology Impact Assessment (*Technikfolgenabschätzung*) approach is particularly important for assessing the long-term societal impact of AI-generated data and models.

Institutions should leverage

- Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs, ORCID, ROR, (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) et al., 2020)) to track data provenance ideally in a standardised and interoperable model like PROV(PROV Working Group, 2013), and ensure long-term accountability.

Institutions should adopt

- Robust archiving, preservation and retention strategies to ensure digital sovereignty in the long term with trusted digital repositories with appropriate certifications. It must be ensured that the chosen repositories respect the licenses and usage restrictions agreed upon, based on above mentioned ethical and legal frameworks.
- Decentralized storage solutions, reducing dependency on single service providers.
- Automated backup and integrity checks, ensuring that long-term accessibility is not compromised.

These recommendations address the multifaceted challenges of long-term data governance in research, categorised by core thematic areas: Data Accessibility & Tracking, Licensing & Attribution, Protection of Sensitive Data, Ethics & Impact Assessment, Provenance & Accountability, and Preservation & Digital Sovereignty. Each area is further divided into actionable steps (implementable under current frameworks), aspirational goals (requiring systemic change or investment), and common practices (widely adopted but often

⁸e.g. confidential computing, trusted execution environments or digital rights management

inconsistently applied). This structure acknowledges the constraints institutions face—whether legal, economic, or political—while clarifying where immediate progress can be made and where broader collaboration is essential.

Table 3. Institutional Responsibilities for Data Governance

Area	Recommendation	Category
Data accessibility & tracking	Ensure persistent accessibility of primary data throughout its lifecycle	Actionable
	Regularly evaluate and reduce reliance on external third-party services	Actionable
	Maintain an inventory of published critical datasets	Actionable
	Monitor data re-use and re-propagation trends	Aspirational
Licensing & attribution	Apply established licensing frameworks (e.g., CC, ODC)	Common practice
	Develop workflows for handling use cases not aligned with institutional policies	Actionable
	Shift responsibility for license selection from individual researchers to a dedicated institutional authority	Actionable
	Develop workflows for non-compliant usage cases (e.g., unauthorised re-use)	Aspirational
Protection of sensitive data	Use NDAs, re-utilisation contracts where necessary	Common practice
	Apply technical safeguards to protect sensitive datasets	Actionable
	Develop institutional policies for dynamic consent (e.g., tiered access à la NAKO or 100,000 Genomes Project)	Aspirational
Ethics & impact assessment	Use Ethical Risk Assessment Frameworks	Actionable

	Integrate Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) (c.f. GDPR Art. 35) into project approval workflows for sensitive data.	Actionable
	Apply Technology Impact Assessment to AI-generated data and models	Aspirational
Provenance & accountability	Use persistent identifiers (DOIs, ORCID, ROR)	Common practice
	Mandate persistent identifiers in institutional repositories and supplying systems	Actionable
	Use interoperable provenance models (e.g., PROV)	Actionable
Preservation & digital sovereignty	Use trusted digital repositories with certifications	Actionable
	Adopt decentralized storage solutions	Aspirational
	Implement automated backups and integrity checks	Common practice

Table 4. Major open and interoperable European cloud infrastructures besides EOSC.

Implementation level	Infrastructure	Interoperability
Operational	GAIA-X	International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) Standards
	CERN OpenStack	EOSC, EGI, and commercial clouds
	DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud	
Pilots	EU Data Spaces	IDSA, GAIA-X
	SovereignEdge.EU	GAIA-X
	Onedata	iRODS

Challenge 8: Ethical challenges

4.8.1 Description of the challenge

Data retention and preservation are crucial for ensuring the long-term value of data and the reproducibility of scientific discoveries. However, long-term data retention also raises critical ethical considerations. Topics such as data retention, accessibility, and data reuse must consider the scientific benefits whilst safeguarding the rights, expectations, and privacy of the individuals or communities represented in the data.

- Privacy and confidentiality risks.** Long-term data retention can introduce various privacy and confidentiality risks, including unauthorized access, data breaches, misuse, and potential non-compliance with evolving legal requirements or institutional policies. Data security is essential for achieving data privacy in general (Shukla et al., 2022). Over time, privacy concerns may also emerge for data involving human participants, as the original consent provided during the research may no longer cover future uses. Additionally, retaining data longer than necessary increases exposure to cyberattacks, since larger and older data stores become more attractive targets for hackers.
- Unclear ownership and stewardship responsibilities.** When research projects conclude, it may become unclear who is responsible for the long-term care, security, and ethical management of the data. Changes in personnel, institutional commitments, or funding can also create gaps in oversight, leading to inconsistent curation practices and loss of accountability. Without clearly defined roles and succession plans, data may be inadequately preserved or fail to meet ethical and legal expectations.
- Lack of institutional knowledge and resources.** Many stakeholders struggle to identify where to seek guidance and best practices. While national legal frameworks may offer partial direction on certain ethical considerations, legislation specific to research data – particularly across diverse disciplinary contexts – requires further development at both national and EU levels (also see Challenge 7).
- Costs and environmental impacts of storage/retention of data.** Long-term data storage carries significant financial and environmental costs. Storing data is costly and requires heavy investments in renewable and non-renewable resources, such as water, land, and even atomic energy, for their maintenance. Therefore, much ethical consideration should go into what is ‘storage worthy’ for the long-term, and in some cases data should be deleted.

- **Unauthorized dissemination and appropriation of indigenous data.** The benefits of open research data infrastructures on increasing dissemination of and access to research results and data are demonstrable in the scientific community, largely with a transitive property to society in general. However, not all communities equally benefit from long-term data retention in European repositories and archives. In fact, doing so without consent from and in meaningful consultation with communities, individuals and descendants of implication⁹ reinforces extractivist, (neo)colonial reproduction and can have tangible consequences for the communities in question. The environmental impact also provides an immense ethical quandary about the sustainability and suitability of long-term data storage and retention, including use of land and resources for data storage facilities. Therefore, we ask, what are the ethical considerations for retaining data collected about and containing knowledges and cultural goods of Indigenous¹⁰ people, including but going beyond personal privacy and intellectual property? What environmental impacts and long-term effects should be weighed and considered?

Below are some examples of challenges to the retention of indigenous data.

- **Narrow scope of data sovereignty.** Since the beginning of colonial contact, Indigenous communities and nations have had to assert the parity of their cultural, societal, economic organization with their European counterparts. Colonial thinking assumes the superiority of the latter and defines sovereignty only in terms of the European nation state.
- **Eurocentrism in archival and library practices.** The practice of organizing and storing information in archives and repositories is itself a product of its cultural context, as are regulatory standards for subject keywords and search terms. The chosen metadata standard as well as the person creating the metadata impart their worldview in the cataloguing or metadata entry process. As such, European institutions inherently center their own ontologies and epistemologies in the organization of FAIR data, often leading to

⁹ Lehrer (2023) expands the notion of “heritage community” arguing for “community of implication” instead: The Council of Europe (CoE) defines a heritage community as “people who value specific aspects of cultural heritage which they wish, within the framework of public action, to sustain and transmit to future generations” [my emphasis] (Council of Europe 2005, 2).

¹⁰ EOSC Support Office Austria, Reichmann, S., Söser, B., & Bohardt, M. (2025). CARE-Principles. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14754234>

misrepresentations and misinterpretations due to lack of knowledge of culturally appropriate engagement with Indigenous data and objects.

- **Narrow scope of mainstream notions of data privacy and sensitive data as pertaining only to individuals.** The MDGov Model puts forth the idea of “collective privacy”, which “recognises and upholds collective rights over information much in the same way that an individual owns and has authority over their personal information” (p. 35).
- **Lack of accountability from European institutions/Actors.** As inheritors of colonial plunder and world views, European institutions and actors are accountable to Indigenous peoples. Acting accountably means engaging in intervening ethical practices that attempt to reduce harm and restore sovereignty to colonized peoples.

4.8.2 Recommendations

For the ethical challenges mentioned above, we recommend the following:

Enhance data security for long-term retention.

This involves implementing practices and processes that protect data from unauthorized access while ensuring it remains accessible to those with proper authorization. Strong data security is essential for safeguarding overall privacy. Repositories should adopt robust security measures such as identity and access management, encryption, tokenization, and comprehensive backup and recovery strategies, all supported by clear data governance and compliance frameworks. In addition, when personal data is involved, GDPR requirements must be followed. This means long-term retention of personal data must be clearly justified and tied to the original purpose for which the data was collected¹¹. Retention periods should not exceed what is necessary, and organisations must implement transparent governance measures, to ensure ongoing compliance and the protection of data subjects’ rights throughout the entire retention period.

Recognize data sovereignty

When retaining data long-term, especially data originating from specific countries, Indigenous communities, or regulated domains, it is essential to respect these sovereignty rights. This includes ensuring that storage locations, access permissions, and future uses comply with the relevant legal, ethical, and cultural frameworks (also see Challenge 7 for

¹¹ General Data Protection Regulation. <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

more details on data sovereignty). Recognizing data sovereignty helps prevent misuse, supports trust, and ensures that data retention practices align with the rights and expectations of the data's rightful owners or stewards. The recognition of the sovereignty of a community of implication entails treating cultural governance within a given territory as distinct, autonomous polities, regardless of residence within (settler) colonial borders or (lack of) official recognition by said nation.

The CARE Principles and the Māori Data Governance Model for Indigenous Data

When looking for guidance, consult the affected communities directly, as only they know what is best for themselves. The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (CARE Principles for short), is such a resource, developed within the context of International Data Week of the Research Data Alliance in 2018, to assert the data needs of Indigenous nations. CARE stands for Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics. Whereas the FAIR Principles focus on making data machine-actionable and provide no ethical guidelines, the CARE Principles promote the human, collectivist stewardship and governance of data. Though not all experience the same effects of colonial ways of thinking and economic extraction, the principles certainly find wider application to other kinds of data and contexts. Indeed, the application of the CARE Principles outside Indigenous communities by Suchikova & Nazarovets (2025) specifically regarding vulnerable populations in war contexts highlights the need for better ethical guidance on the sharing of research data in general.

The Māori Data Governance Model¹² is an example of a comprehensive, community designed and organised application of the CARE Principles. While based on Māori values, concepts and experiences, the notion of treating data stewardship holistically and ethics not only being an aspect thereof but rather the pillars of a governance framework are arguably applicable to any data context . The Māori Data Governance Model puts forward a model of "Governance of Data and Data for Governance" encouraging the creation of data governance structures that take the time and energy to reflect collectively on ethical issues, create policies that propose concrete action, and hold different actors accountable.

Local Contexts, an Indigenous-led organization based in the Navajo Nation, has developed pictographic Traditional Knowledge Labels to help digital systems apply the CARE Principles when managing Indigenous knowledge¹³.

¹² The Māori Data Governance Model:

https://www.kahuiraraunga.io/_files/ugd/b8e45c_803c03ffe532414183afcd8b9ced10dc.pdf

¹³ TK Labels. <https://localcontexts.org/labels/traditional-knowledge-labels/>

Consult Communities, Individuals and Descendants on Preferred Procedures for Data Retention or Repatriation

Personal relationships cannot be replaced by policy documents. In any given case, it is best to consult implicated communities, individuals, descendants regarding what they wish for the storage of their data. That being said, if applicable, do refer to the data governance policy of the community in question as a starting point.

Accept Responsibility and Act Relationally and Comply with data policies

Researchers and data stewards should actively accept responsibility for the ethical management of data throughout its lifecycle. This includes engaging with stakeholders, such as participants, communities, and institutions, to respect their rights, expectations, and perspectives. Additionally, all data handling must comply with applicable laws, regulations, and organizational policies to ensure accountability, trustworthiness, and the long-term integrity of data.

Regarding the Indigenous Data, it is also the responsibility of researchers and employees at European libraries, archives, and museums and research producing institutions to inform themselves about the CARE principles and of the data policies of the communities with whom they work.

Challenge 9: Trust

4.9.1 Description of the challenge

Trust in data and in data-retention practices is a prerequisite for the reuse, acceptance, and reliance on data that need to be preserved, thereby enabling its long-term scientific value and reusability. This includes trust that the data are scientifically sound, valid, and correctly documented, as well as confidence in the transparency of their provenance, versioning, and authenticity. Researchers and data providers must be able to verify where the data came from, how they were generated and processed, and whether any changes have been made over time. Clear documentation, robust metadata, and traceable preservation actions help users assess data quality and reduce uncertainties. Without such trust, even well-preserved datasets risk being underused or considered unreliable in future research.

- **Provenance.** Gaps may occur when critical contextual, methodological, or procedural information is missing, fragmented, or undocumented. This can be caused by:

- Inconsistent documentation practices if researchers use varying templates, file-naming conventions, or metadata standards, leading to nonuniform records.
 - Loss during workflow transitions, as software environments, or repositories, intermediate processing steps are often lost or overwritten when data move between instruments.
 - Legacy data and format obsolescence since historical datasets may come before current metadata standards or have been stored in formats that can no longer be parsed or read.
 - Insufficient metadata policies as many repositories do curate data at deposit but lack mandatory fields for detailed methodological or provenance metadata.
 - Lack of incentive for researchers, who may see little reward for capturing provenance rigorously as it is labour-intensive, especially under pressure to publish.
- **Versioning.** Version control issues arise because many scientific data systems were not designed with dynamic data management in mind. Users cannot confidently determine whether a dataset is accurate, or traceable.
 - **Authenticity.** Files can be altered accidentally during processing or deliberately through falsification or fabrication without leaving a detectable trace if integrity checks are not in place. Copying, merging, or reformatting data may also introduce untracked modifications. Metadata critical for verifying authenticity (e.g., creator, timestamp, acquisition method) can become detached or lost, especially during format conversions or migrations.

Trust also implies that repositories will protect and preserve the data responsibly, thus has data retention and custodianship dimensions, as transparency is required on:

- **Retention policies.** They are not merely administrative documents but the formal expression of a repository's commitment to long-term stewardship, accountability, and sustainability. When such policies are unclear or missing, stakeholders cannot be confident that data will remain accessible, authentic, or safe over time. Custodial credibility declines when retention policies are absent or poorly implemented, leaving users unsure whether the data they deposit will be preserved in the long term.

- **Assessment/reassessment processes.** If data subjects (i.e., research study participants) don't know how long their data will be kept or how often that decision will be reviewed, they may feel uncertain about how their information is being handled. If retention decisions are not revisited, data might be held longer than participants expected or agreed to. This can be perceived as a breach of trust, even if no legal rule is broken. For sensitive studies (e.g., health, social, or community-based research), data subjects trust that their data will not be used indefinitely or outside of purpose. A lack of reassessment weakens that confidence.
- **Integrity, security.** Depositors share their personal or sensitive information under the expectation that it will be protected. If stakeholders can't trust that data have been preserved correctly, they can't trust the research outcomes based on them. Furthermore, a single incident of lost, tampered, or leaked data can undo years of credibility.

4.9.2 Recommendations

Researchers as depositors and repositories as custodians of data storage and retention both have important roles in fostering trust throughout the data-retention process. Several actions can be taken to strengthen this trust.

Researcher (depositor)

- Robust provenance tracking: Implement persistent identifiers, versioning, and standardized metadata that capture context, methodology, and processing steps.
- Community-driven quality standards: Encourage disciplinary groups to define minimum metadata and validation practices, with accreditation where feasible.
- Transparent peer/data review: Extend peer review to datasets, involving domain experts to assess integrity and adequacy.
- Automated checks, audit trails.

Custodian/repository

- Clear governance models: Define and communicate roles, responsibilities, and succession plans for data stewardship.
- Regular reappraisal policies: Formalize processes to periodically evaluate datasets for ongoing scientific value, ethical compliance, and custodial feasibility.

- Trusted digital repository (TDR) certification: Promote certification frameworks (e.g., CoreTrustSeal) to ensure repositories follow transparent and auditable practices.

General Discussion

Through examining the challenges and potential solutions related to data retention, we have identified several recurring factors across different issues. These include gaps in funding and policy, limited awareness and understanding of data retention, and the lack of clear standards and guidelines. These issues are often complex and not easily addressed through single, one-size-fits-all recommendations. Instead, they require further investment in understanding how to better engage the relevant stakeholders to support data preservation activities.

Funding constraints have been listed as a key challenge for data retention, and appear in several other challenges, such as Challenge 5 Understanding the value of data holding and Challenge 8 Ethical challenges. As described in Challenge 1, we face multiple issues, including funding misalignment, unclear responsibilities, weak coordination among beneficiaries, and underfunded archives. Current funding schemes typically support activities that take place during a project’s lifetime, which is often limited (e.g., 3–5 years). However, most digital preservation costs arise *after* a project ends. This affects decisions about which data to preserve, especially given that long-term storage is costly and requires both renewable and non-renewable resources. Divergent policies also interact with funding programmes, particularly when estimating long-term preservation costs. Centralised funding mechanisms could be one potential solution, particularly for the preservation of datasets originally generated through public funding. Similarly, the development of centrally funded digital preservation infrastructures may further strengthen and sustain long-term data retention practices.

Limited awareness and understanding of data retention also pose a significant challenge. This issue is evident among both researchers (as data providers) and funders, who often underestimate the importance of long-term data retention (Challenge 2 and 1). For many researchers, resources such as time, funding, and attention are primarily directed toward data acquisition, processing, and producing publishable results. As a result, data retention is frequently treated as a secondary concern, and the long-term value of data is often overlooked during the project lifecycle. This challenge is also present within domain-specific scientific communities (Challenge 3). The scientific communities often underestimate the importance of data preservation—both within their own discipline and in relation to other fields—leading to insufficient consensus on defining core preservation metadata and a

limited appreciation of cross-disciplinary data value. As described in Challenge 1, funding schemes typically support data retention only for a limited number of years. Long-term preservation within and beyond this period generally lacks dedicated financial support, reflecting a broader lack of understanding of the importance and long-term value of research data for scientific communities and society. Furthermore, Challenge 8 (Ethical Challenges) highlights the lack of institutional knowledge and resources. Researchers and data stewards frequently rely on national legal frameworks and both national and EU-level legislation, underscoring the need for clearer guidance and stronger institutional support.

Challenge 4 highlights **the lack of standards and guidelines for data retention**, a gap that is also evident in other areas such as Challenge 2 (Lack of expertise) and Challenge 3 (Discipline- and content-specific challenges). There is absence of adequate security management practices, particularly regarding sensitive data and the protection levels required. Research disciplines and content types differ widely in their retention needs, preservation practices, technical requirements, preferred preservation formats, and access protocols. Without clear and consistently applied standards, these differences become even more difficult to manage. Moreover, the lack of systematic assessment and reassessment procedures contributes to issues of trust and transparency in long-term data preservation.

Many of the challenges identified in this paper have been recognised for years, yet progress remains uneven. Our Task Force members will continue to explore these dimensions in greater depth and to provide more detailed insights in the coming updated version of this document.

Appendix 1. Collection of Possible Ethical Questions by Question Type

Topic	Questions
Copyright/Intellectual Property	Which knowledge systems are reflected by the data? Who produced the data? Are the recorders of the data and the producers of the data the same? Who is/are the owner(s) of the data? Who has the right to close or open access to the data? Are there living descendants or communities that have a relation to data collected many years ago? Do they know the data exists?
Accessibility & Findability	Should the metadata about the data/object be findable? For whom should the (meta)data be accessible? Under what conditions? What are potential impacts or harms of storing the data, making it findable, and/or accessible?
Recirculation/Repatriation	Should the data be repatriated to an indigenous nation or community of implication? Should the current holding institution notify the community of the existence of the data? What does the community want to happen with the data?
Compliance	Do our institutional data governance structures and policies address these ethical concerns? If not, how can the institution/policies be changed to address them?
Roles & Responsibilities	What are the roles and responsibilities of an employee of the holding institution, researcher, data steward, user, etc.?

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